

Social Inspiration in Southern Vietnamese Novels in the First Half of the Twentieth Century

Dr. Truong Thi Linh¹, Dr. Tran Thi My Hien²

^{1,2}Faculty of Education, Thu Dau Mot University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

ABSTRACT: The purpose of this article is to affirm that social inspiration in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century is a form of inspiration that possesses continuity in the history of Vietnamese literature from the past to the present. Although this type of inspiration is often mentioned in literary studies, it has not been examined in a comprehensive manner, especially in Southern Vietnamese novels of this period.

In the context of Vietnamese society undergoing significant changes in economic, political, cultural, and social life, Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century reflected issues of morality, lifestyle, class stratification, and the life of urban residents. Through the analysis of several representative novels, the article shows that social inspiration is first expressed in the criticism of moral degradation and pragmatic lifestyles in contemporary society. At the same time, these works also clearly depict the reality of the ruling class with its injustices and social contradictions. In addition, the impoverished and backward economic life of the people is also reflected as an important factor in this period.

From this, the article affirms that, alongside personal inspiration and celebratory inspiration, social inspiration is a dominant form of inspiration in novels of this period.

KEYWORDS: inspiration, social inspiration, personal inspiration, psychological-social novel, Southern Vietnamese novel, historical novel

I. INTRODUCTION

Inspiration is often understood as a special psychological state of the author during the creation of a literary work. However, this understanding limits the conceptual scope of the term. Therefore, beyond being a special and momentary psychological state, inspiration is also the author's passion to affirm a belief of a more enduring nature. That is, inspiration is not merely an individual psychological impulse at a given moment, but an ideology that the author adheres to throughout the process of artistic creation. In other words, inspiration can be regarded as an "internal logic" that governs the way the author selects themes, subjects, characters, and language in creative practice.

On that basis, social inspiration can be understood as a specific form of literary inspiration, in which the writer directs attention to social issues, human life, and concrete historical transformations. Social inspiration not only reflects reality but also participates in the construction and interrogation of discourses on power, morality, and human condition within particular historical contexts. Thus, inspiration and social inspiration are not merely matters of creative psychology, but also categories of a historical, discursive, and political nature, contributing to shaping the intellectual depth and social value of literary texts.

For that reason, we develop the article "social inspiration in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century" as an illustration of the creative practice of Southern Vietnamese writers during a transitional period.

2. RESEARCH CONTENT

2.1. The concept of inspiration and social inspiration

Social inspiration (thể: life; sự: affairs; social: affairs of life) is a type of inspiration in which the writer expresses their perception of reality, describes life as it is, and draws material from real life (through the writer's own observation or information conveyed in daily newspapers) to put into writing. Under the influence of social inspiration, realist writers in the early twentieth century were able to: raise issues present in life; partly explain the nature of society, the oppression and injustices that poor and voiceless people had to endure; perceive changes in the social structure; and express opposing viewpoints between generations—the old and the young, the rich and the poor, and so on. This is most clearly manifested in literary works (here, novels), helping readers in the past

Social Inspiration in Southern Vietnamese Novels in the First Half of the Twentieth Century

as well as today better understand a bygone historical period than dry reports in fields such as culture, politics, economy, science, and morality. All of this enables contemporary readers to have a more objective view of the past and, through that, to anticipate the future.

With social inspiration, writers focus on depicting: the serious moral decline during the transitional period; the reality of the ruling class (mandarins, feudal landlords, capitalist owners, etc.) of the time; and the stagnant, backward, and impoverished economic life of the people. Finally, it involves a re-evaluation of life's values and the ways in which people adapt when their living conditions undergo fundamental changes. Writers concentrated on portraying life, especially in the genre of the psychological-social novel, addressing all aspects of life such as morality and lifestyles in old and new families, conflicts between parents and children, between husbands and wives, as well as human concerns with money and power.

2.2. Issues of morality and lifestyle in the transitional period

During the transitional period, morality and lifestyle are sensitive issues that are posed as matters of survival among different viewpoints of various generations. In this context, the clarification and maintenance of personal ethics, social morality, and proper lifestyles become important goals in building a healthy, civilized, and sustainable society. This is because morality can be understood as a set of principles and values that guide human actions. It determines what is right and wrong, just and unjust, moral and immoral. Morality not only requires individuals to act in accordance with social rules and standards, but also demands respect, honesty, and responsibility. It reflects humanity and kindness in each person's thinking and actions.

Modern life is full of temptations, injustices, and invisible pressures, which easily cause people to lose themselves and their inclination toward goodness. However, alongside the changes in morality and lifestyles of a non-traditional nature (as mentioned above) among a portion of the population, there still exist individuals who maintain proper lifestyles, uphold morality, and live in a civilized manner consistent with social progress. These issues occur daily in the press and in everyday life, enabling writers to draw linguistic and experiential material from reality and bring it into their works. This serves as evidence for the emergence of contemporary novels during this period in Southern Vietnam.

2.2.1. Reality of the contemporary feudal and ruling class

First, realist inspiration with a social nature in the depiction of official life is one of the main inspirations in realist novels of this period. Normally, the mandarin class was supposed to be an intellectual class entrusted by the government with the responsibility of caring for the people's lives and protecting them. However, besides those good officials who devoted themselves wholeheartedly to the people and the nation, there were still corrupt and degenerate mandarins, as well as kings who indulged only in pleasure and luxury such as Lê Long Đĩnh (Tiền Lê vận Mạc - Phạm Minh Kiên), Bùi Khắc Phục, Nguyễn Thành Nhơn (Gia Long tâu quốc - Tân Dân Tử)... The oppression and suppression of innocent people appear as widespread phenomena across both the South and the North, in both rural and urban areas, in novels of this period.

In *Sống chết mặc bay* (Phạm Duy Tốn), we see irresponsible officials who are indifferent to the life and death of the people. Southern realist novels, meanwhile, focus on portraying the ruling class as having degenerated into extremely selfish, greedy, and cruel individuals, especially in the genre of psychological-social novels by Hồ Biểu Chánh. For example, *Bá Hộ Cao* (Ngọn cỏ gió đùa - Hồ Biểu Chánh) harms Lê Văn Đố; *Hương hào Hội* commits adultery with a tenant farmer's wife and then seeks to bribe his way out of punishment (*Cha con nghĩa nặng* - Hồ Biểu Chánh); *Trần Tấn Thân* (Chúa tàu Kim Quy) rapes Lê Thủ Nghĩa's younger sister and then bribes to have him imprisoned; the district official (*Ngọn cỏ gió đùa* - Hồ Biểu Chánh) tries every means to force Lý Ánh Nguyệt to serve his desires... All of these contribute to constructing a society in which cruelty and tyranny prevail. Huỳnh Thị Lan Phương and Nguyễn Văn Nở (2010) affirm that "Hồ Biểu Chánh is a writer who reflects reality in a truthful manner."

Second, social inspiration regarding official life is also expressed through the contradictions and conflicts between the peasantry and the mandarin class in both rural and urban areas. More broadly, it extends to the conflicts between poor intellectuals and capitalist owners in the cities; between Vietnamese people and foreigners (notably the Hoa Kiều, Chà Và, Indians, and the French...). This is clearly reflected in several novels such as *Hà Hương phong nguyệt* (Lê Hoàng Mưu, 1912), *Trường tình bí mật* (Dương Minh Đạt, 1929), *Lửa tình* (Trần Quang Nghiệp, 1931)...

In *Trường tình bí mật*, Dương Minh Đạt focuses on depicting the opposition between Vietnamese people and "other races," including resident foreigners such as the Chệt (Hoa Kiều), Chà Và (Indians), and Cao Man (Cambodians)... In this novel, Dương Minh Đạt primarily portrays economic opposition: Vietnamese people are exploited not only in terms of labor but also material wealth by capitalist owners (supported by French colonialism). Not only are they exploited in terms of labor and money, but they are also treated by capitalist owners/the ruling class as tools for the release of sexual desire (*Lửa tình* - Trần Quang Nghiệp), making human values and human life extremely cheap in such a turbulent period.

2.2.2. Impoverished and backward economic life

First, inspiration concerning poor people and poor intellectuals in rural or urban areas struggling with daily "food, clothing, and money." For them, mere survival is already an extremely arduous and miserable task. These aspects can be found in works such as: *Cay đắng mùi đời*, *Tình mộng*, *Con nhà giàu*, *Con nhà nghèo*, *Người thất chí*, *Ngọn cỏ gió đùa*... (Hồ Biểu Chánh); *Cô ba Trành*

Social Inspiration in Southern Vietnamese Novels in the First Half of the Twentieth Century

(Nguyễn Ý Bửu); Chén cơm lạt của người thất nghiệp (Sơn Vương); Biển cả thuyền con (Trần Quang Nghiệp), Con nhà nghèo (Nguyễn Bửu Mộc)...

Second, social inspiration related to the theme of unfortunate and orphaned people—those who stand on the margins of the arena of social power—carries a tragic nature. When portraying such figures, the pen of novelists closely follows the actual conditions of people's lives. This type of inspiration can be seen in several novels such as: Thầy Lazarô Phiền (Nguyễn Trọng Quản); Tình mộng (Hồ Biểu Chánh); Nghĩa hiệp kỳ duyên (Nguyễn Chánh Sắt)...

Thầy Phiền spent his entire childhood living in hiding, in circumstances where death could come at any moment; therefore, his psychological state is a negative one. "The suffering I have endured has gone beyond my capacity." (Nguyễn Trọng Quản, 1999, p. 22). Chăng Cà Mum (Nghĩa hiệp kỳ duyên - Nguyễn Chánh Sắt) is a girl separated from her family, oppressed in every way by her adoptive family, and treated like a domestic animal, "pushed and shoved like that girl and pointed at (...)" (Nguyễn Chánh Sắt, 2002, p. 41). Phạm Linh Chi (Chén cơm lạt của người thất nghiệp - Sơn Vương), unable to find a job, having no money to support his wife and children, and having no rice to eat—left with only a bowl of cold rice to get through the day, which is then taken away by a stray dog—thus intends to act recklessly to free himself and his loved ones. Poor people (Khóc thẳm - Hồ Biểu Chánh) have to borrow money and rent land at exorbitant prices just to maintain their lives, inadvertently enriching heartless wealthy individuals such as Vĩnh Thái...

Third, social inspiration related to productive labor life and the religious spiritual life of Southern Vietnamese peasants. First is the traditional wet-rice cultivation and the ways of making a living of poor farmers in: Cay đắng mùi đời (Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1923), Con nhà nghèo (Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1930), Biển cả thuyền con (Trần Quang Nghiệp, 1931), Hai Thà cưới vợ (Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1944)... The miserable and difficult lives: of Chí Đại and Bạch Tuyết in Ai làm được (Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1922); of the family of clerk Phạm Linh Chi (Chén cơm lạt của người thất nghiệp - Sơn Vương, 1931); Biển cả thuyền con (Trần Quang Nghiệp, 1931), Hồ thẳm (Nguyễn Bửu Mộc, 1932), Phụng (Người thất chí - Hồ Biểu Chánh, 1938), Ngọc Lam Điền [publisher and first publication year not yet identified] (Phú Đức)...

With this inspiration, the material and spiritual life of poor people appears very clearly. This is because there is a reality that the agricultural production life of Southern Vietnamese peasants is entirely dependent on the weather and on luck. If the weather is favorable, farming can yield enough to support a family until the next season; if not, after paying rent for the land, nothing remains—either they must go hungry or find other means of subsistence until the next harvest. This is because they have no means to improve their productivity. This is reflected very clearly and explicitly in Con nhà nghèo, Khóc thẳm (Hồ Biểu Chánh)...

Next is the religious spiritual life reflected in works such as: Thầy Lazarô Phiền (Nguyễn Trọng Quản), Tôi có tội (Phú Đức, 1935), Bà chúa đèn vàng [first publication year unknown] (Phú Đức)

3. CONCLUSION

From the examination of thể sự inspiration in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century, it can be seen that this is not merely a mode of reflecting reality but also a form of inspiration that is continuous and inherited within the course of national literary history. In the context of a transitional society marked by profound changes in economic, political, cultural, and social life, Southern Vietnamese writers demonstrated a keen awareness of the issues of their time through the depiction of aspects such as morality, lifestyle, class stratification, and urban life.

Thể sự inspiration in these works is first manifested in the critical stance toward moral decline and pragmatic lifestyles, while also clearly reflecting the injustices and social contradictions within society, particularly among the ruling class. In addition, the portrayal of the impoverished and backward economic conditions of the people contributes to highlighting the instability and complexity of this historical period. In this way, Southern Vietnamese novels not only reflect reality but also express a clear social consciousness and critical attitude on the part of the writers.

From these analyses, it can be affirmed that, alongside personal inspiration and celebratory inspiration, thể sự inspiration plays a dominant role in Southern Vietnamese novels in the first half of the twentieth century. At the same time, the study of this aspect contributes to a clearer understanding of the characteristics of Southern literature in the process of the modernization of Vietnamese literature, while also opening up further approaches to the study of literary inspirations and discourses in other historical periods.

REFERENCES

- 1) Huỳnh Thị Lan Phương, & Nguyễn Văn Nờ. (2010). Cảm hứng thể sự - điểm gặp gỡ và khác biệt giữa tiểu thuyết Hồ Biểu Chánh với tiểu thuyết miền Bắc giai đoạn 1900–1930 [Social inspiration – points of convergence and divergence between Hồ Biểu Chánh's novels and Northern Vietnamese novels in the period 1900–1930]. Tạp chí Nghiên cứu văn học [Journal of Literary Studies], (4), 35–53. hobieuchanh.com
- 2) Nguyễn Trọng Quản. (1999). Thầy Lazarô Phiền [Thầy Lazarô Phiền]. In Cao Xuân Mỹ (Ed.), Văn xuôi Nam Bộ nửa đầu thế kỷ XX [Southern Vietnamese prose in the first half of the twentieth century] (Vol. 1, pp. 13–37). Ho Chi Minh: Văn nghệ; Trung tâm nghiên cứu Quốc học.
- 3) Nguyễn Chánh Sắt. (2002). Nghĩa hiệp kỳ duyên [A chivalric and romantic tale]. Ho Chi Minh: Văn nghệ.